

ON THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF INDIAN BENTONITES. PART I.

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The swelling and thixotropy of seven natural Indian bentonites in relation to their chemical composition, exchangeable bases, and base binding capacity have been studied.

Bentonite is being increasingly used in the preparation of muds for rotary drilling. When added in small quantities to a clay suspension, bentonite stabilises the mud and induces thixotropy in it. Freundlich, Schmidt and Lindau (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1932, **36**, 43) have studied the influence of various alkalis and salts on the thixotropy and allied properties of a hydrogen bentonite, prepared from the naturally occurring sodium bentonite of Wyoming (U.S.A.). Bentonite deposits in different countries have variable properties and the need for investigations on Indian clay minerals, similar to bentonite, has been pointed out by Mitra and Reid (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1938, p. 99).

In the present investigation bentonite samples* from different localities of India were taken ; they are named according to the localities of their occurrence :—

Kashmir—KB, Akli—AB, Hatikidhani—HB, Bhadres—BB,
Maober—MB, Dodia Bisale—DB. Nimli Nadi—NB.

The chemical composition of bentonites approximates to that of the montmorillonite type of clay. Ross and Shannon (*J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1926, **9**, 77) propose the formula Al_2O_3 , CaO, $5SiO_2$ and Marshall (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, **41**, 935) represents it as Al_2O_3 , MgO, $5SiO_2$, nH_2O , while Hofmann *et al* (*Z. Krist.*, 1933, **86**, 340) believe that the fundamental structure is Al_2O_3 , $4SiO_2$, nH_2O (prophyllite).

Bentonites possess a layer lattice structure as shown by X-ray investigations (Hofmann *et al*, *loc. cit.*). Polar liquids like water can enter in between the layers forcing them apart. Several special properties of bentonites namely thixotropy, high swelling and large sedimentation volume are now ascribed to this property.

The maximum distance to which the layers can be separated by means of water, however, depends on the saturating exchangeable cation. Marshall

* The bentonite samples have been kindly supplied by the Assam Oil Company, Ltd.

(*loc. cit.*) has calculated that the mean separation in the case of H- or Ca-bentonite is 14Å, while in the case of Na-bentonite it is greater than 23Å. The thixotropic property of bentonite is also destroyed when exchangeable sodium is replaced by hydrogen or calcium.

The following properties of several Indian bentonites have been dealt with in the present paper :—

- (a) Chemical composition.
- (b) Base saturation capacity and exchangeable cations.
- (c) Swelling in distilled water.
- (d) Sedimentation volume and sedimentation velocity in distilled water.
- (e) Thixotropy in distilled water.

A comparative study of the influence of saturating cations on the properties of the bentonites has been undertaken.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

The samples were all powdered and sieved through a 70 mesh sieve. Chemical analyses were carried out by the sodium carbonate fusion method (Wright, "Soil Analysis," 1934, p. 153). The results are expressed as the percentage composition by weight.

TABLE I.

Sample.	SiO ₂ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	MgO.	Na ₂ O + K ₂ O (by diff.).	Loss at 110°.	Loss on ignition.
KB	52.4	17.0	1.8	1.9	1.3	2.5	10.3	12.8
AB	54.9	19.4	6.8	0.1	0.0	2.1	10.9	5.8
HB	51.4	21.4	6.8	0.7	1.9	3.1	8.7	6.0
BB	52.4	24.1	6.6	0.4	0.4	0.7	8.1	8.3
MB	48.3	22.7	9.3	0.7	0.3	1.3	7.7	9.7
DB	51.4	24.7	5.2	0.6	1.5	2.2	7.4	7.0
NB	52.1	28.2	5.0	0.4	0.3	1.6	4.1	8.3

The base saturation capacity has been measured by Parker's method (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1929, 21, 1030) and by Schollenberger's method (*Science*, 1927, 65, 552) and the individual bases by Schollenberger's method only.* In Table II, the results of base exchange measurements are compared with the SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio of the various bentonites. The exchangeable bases and the base saturation capacity were measured at *p*_H 7, and are expressed in milli-equivalents per 100 g. of bentonite dried at 110°.

* The minerals do not contain CaCO₃ and the amount of exchangeable Ca as obtained by leaching with sodium chloride (Wright, *loc. cit.*) was practically the same as obtained by Schollenberger's method.

TABLE II.

Sample.	$\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$	ρ_{π} of 5% suspension.	Base sat. capacity.	E x c h a n g e a b l e			Total exchangeable bases.
				Ca.	Mg.	Na + K.	
KB	5.0	6.8	100	66	1	28	95
AB	4.8	7.2	92	5	0	85	90
HB	4.0	7.1	80	13	19	44	76
BB	4.0	7.1	74	11	15	39	65
MB	3.7	7.1	81	15	16	45	76
DB	3.5	7.4	65	11	9	42	62
NB	3.2	6.7	64	9	9	40	58

Thus all the bentonites are more or less saturated with cations. KB is a calcium bentonite and is expected to have some unusual properties from the rest. AB contains mainly sodium and very small amount of Ca, the rest containing all the replaceable cations in various proportions. The base saturation capacity increases with the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio.

Swelling.

By the term swelling is meant the expansion of the pore-space under the influence of a solvent. In order to get the true swelling of a dry gel one has to subtract the volume of the original pore-space from the total volume of liquid taken in when the swelling substance is in contact with it.

Swelling is a phenomena comparable to osmosis and as such swelling can be measured by the pressure developed on the side of the swelling substance separated by a membrane through which the solid cannot pass.

Since swelling pressure is small for bentonites Freundlich *et al* (*loc. cit.*) devised an apparatus for measuring the volume of liquid taken in instead of pressure. If the original pore-space of the material is known the amount of swelling can be easily obtained. For bentonities the swelling is generally several times greater than the pore-space and the total sorption of water may be taken as proportional to swelling for comparative studies.

The swelling has been measured by a simplified form of the apparatus used by Freundlich *et al* (*loc. cit.*). In Fig. 1 G is a glass gooch in

which the substance is placed on the filter-bed F, M is a capillary burette reading directly up to 0.01 c.c.

Fig. 1

Evaporation is prevented by means of a rubber stopper S and the capillaries P P'. The apparatus is filled upto F and the end of the microburette with distilled water. One gram of the sieved samples of the bentonite dried at 110° is quickly dropped in and the stopper is closed. The rate of absorption of water in c.c. is measured from the movement of the water meniscus in the burette.*

TABLE III.

Time.	KB.	AB.	HB.	BB.	MB.	DB.	NB.
	Water absorbed per g. of oven-dried bentonite in c.c.						
30 sec.	1.26	0.48	0.48	0.39	0.48	0.55	0.30
1 min.	1.36	0.59	0.57	0.46	0.57	0.64	0.38
2	1.41	0.75	0.70	0.56	0.70	0.76	0.46
5	1.45	1.07	0.94	0.76	0.93	0.98	0.62
10	1.48	1.42	1.22	1.00	1.21	1.25	0.77
20	1.50	1.90	1.55	1.31	1.53	1.58	0.95
40	1.52	2.57	1.91	1.67	1.88	2.00	1.09
60	1.53	3.02	2.04	1.81	2.01	2.17	1.145
100	1.54	3.40	2.10	1.94	2.06	2.30	1.195
180	1.56	3.72	2.14	2.02	2.10	2.40	1.24
Final value after 2 days	1.64	5.01	2.52	2.20	2.49	2.79	1.57

* Faver and Winterkorn (*Soil Science*, 1934, 38, 291) have also measured swelling by the same method.

The results with AB are plotted in Fig. 2, where the curve obtained by Freundlich and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) on natural Wyoming bentonite is given for comparison.*

The high swelling of AB is obviously due to its high percentage of univalent cations. KB shows a swelling curve different from the rest in that the swelling is almost complete in 10 minutes. This is to be ascribed to the high percentage of exchangeable calcium. The swelling of KB is comparable to the case of electrolysed bentonite studied by Freundlich *et al* (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

Sedimentation Volume and Sedimentation Velocity.

The rate of sedimentation was measured in 10 c. c. cylinders graduated to 0.1 c. c. The results with 5% bentonites dried at 100° are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Sample.	KB.	BR.	BR.	MR.	DB.	NB.
Sedimentation volume in c.c. at the time t						
Time (t)						
30 mins.	1.2	8.1	9.1	9.1	9.3	10.0
1 hr.	1.3	7.0	8.6	8.6	8.8	10.0
2	1.4	6.3	8.3	8.2	8.1	10.0
3	1.4	6.1	8.1	8.0	7.8	9.95
5	1.45	5.9	7.9	7.8	7.5	9.95
10	1.55	5.85	7.65	7.5	7.0	9.0
20	1.6	5.8	7.5	7.3	6.7	9.85
Final constant value	1.7	5.7	7.4	7.2	6.6	6.0

* Freundlich *et al* made measurements with 0.3 g. of the sample; their results are divided by 0.3 to give the swelling for 1. g. of the bentonite.

The bentonite AB was thixotropic at this concentration and KB showed differential settling with a turbidity in the upper layer. Excepting NB the sedimentation volume reaches a limiting value practically after one day. The sedimentation volume of NB diminished almost linearly with time for about a week.

Thixotropy.

The time for sol to gel transformation is known to vary largely with the concentration of the suspension, the cross-section of the measuring apparatus and the temperature (Freundlich, "Thixotropy," Paris, 1935).

Definite weights of the powdered and sieved samples were added to 2 c. c. of distilled water in measuring cylinders of the same cross-section (1.14 sq. cm). The time of solidification was measured after the samples had been in contact with the liquid for one day by which equilibrium between them may be expected to have been established. The time of solidification was not satisfactorily reproducible but since it varies exponentially with the solid concentration, an approximate value of the former is sufficient for comparative measurements. The logarithm of the average time has been plotted in Fig. 3 against the percentage concentration of the undried bentonite (drying often reduces thixotropic properties). A linear relationship is observed.

Assuming that the suspensions are thixotropic between setting times 1 sec and 24 hours, the range of thixotropic concentration are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Bentonite (air dried) per 100 c. c. of water showing thixotropy.

Bentonite.	Min.	Max.
AB	5.0	6.5
HB	16.5	24.5
BB	9.1	12.2
MB	9.8	13.0
DB	10.7	13.5
NB	13.7	18.4

KB shows gelation by differential settling

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Besides the time of gelation one must also know the rate of change of viscosity during the time of gelation and the gel strength before a complete picture of the thixotropic properties of a material can be formed. Further measurements in this line are in progress.

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